

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF NADALOL LOADED MULTIPLE EMULSION

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Abstract:

Multiple emulsions have been proposed to have numerous uses including their use for enhancement of bioavailability or as a prolonged drug delivery system. But the inherent instability of this system needs to be overcome before they find potential application in pharmaceuticals. Multiple emulsions are often stabilized using a combination of hydrophilic and hydrophobic surfactants. The ratio of these surfactants is important in achieving stable multiple emulsions. Nadolol was selected as a model drug to study the potential of multiple emulsion to improve bioavailability with the hypothesis that improvement of drug release profile will reflect the enhancement of bioavailability of the drug. The objective of this study was to prepare multiple emulsion of Nadolol by two step emulsification using different nonionic surfactants, Tweens & Spans, and evaluate for percentage drug entrapment, zeta potential, Globule size and in vitro drug release. All the observations and recorded data were identical to the values reported in literature. Calibration curves of Nadolol in methanol and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) were prepared using a double beam UV-visible spectrophotometer. The different formulations of multiple emulsion were evaluated on the basis of their drug entrapment efficiency and globule size. The multiple emulsion was stable and had good entrapment efficiency. There were no drug-excipients interactions. From the result and conclusion of the research work we can summarize that the multiple emulsions can be optimized for good globule size and higher entrapment efficiency by optimizing different formulation variables like type and proportion of primary and secondary emulsifier incorporated in Primary Emulsion and Multiple Emulsion.

Keywords: Nadolol, Multiple emulsion, Non-ionic surfactant, Bioavailability

Introduction:

Multiple emulsions are systems that combine both water-in-oil (W/O) and oil-in-water (O/W) structures. To prepare these emulsions using the two-step method, at least two emulsifiers are required: one with a specific hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value to stabilize the primary W/O emulsion, and another with a higher HLB value to stabilize the secondary O/W emulsion. Typically, a low HLB surfactant, known for its high hydrophobicity, is added to the oil phase.¹

Multiple emulsions can be utilized for various applications including controlled or sustained release, targeted delivery, taste masking, enhancing bioavailability, and enzyme immobilization^{2,3}. Research has focused on how additives such as lipid phases, emulsifiers, electrolytes, biopolymers, and sugars affect the external phases of these emulsions^{4,5}. Additionally, the methods used for dispersing these emulsions are crucial for their stability. In drug delivery, especially with W/O/W emulsions, it is vital to achieve a highly stable system with numerous submicron-sized water droplets⁶. The stability of such emulsions is influenced by the strength of the interfacial

film, which is determined by the elasticity of the hydrophobic surfactant in the external aqueous phase^{7,8}. Long-term stability and the formation of metastable structures are affected by the osmotic pressure of the inner droplets⁹. The microfluidic technique offers significant advantages for creating multiple emulsions due to its precise control over emulsion characteristics, making it scalable and suitable for producing complex emulsions and microcapsules.

Developing multiple emulsion dosage forms with specific active ingredients can be challenging. The goal is to enhance the release rate and bioavailability of Nadolol compared to traditional solid oral dosage forms. This challenge arises due to the pharmacokinetic issues related to oral absorption and disposition of Nadolol. Its oral bioavailability ranges between 25% and 40% with notable variations among individuals. Nadolol has poor solubility in acidic solutions but is slightly soluble in alkaline solutions, forming a more soluble barium complex in the neutral conditions of the gastrointestinal tract. Additionally, Nadolol's diffusion potential decreases as the pH shifts from acidic to near-neutral in the gastrointestinal tract. Addressing these biopharmaceutical properties to improve release and bioavailability while minimizing variability is complex. Therefore, developing a Nadolol multiple emulsion with a rapid and sustained release profile and improved bioavailability, along with reduced variability, would be highly beneficial. The goal of this study is to develop and evaluate such a multiple emulsion formulation for Nadolol.

Materials and methods:

Materials:

Nadalol is procured from Yarrow chem pvt Ltd. Span and Tween 80 purchased from Sd fine chemicals, liquid paraffin oil from Yarrow chem.

Methodology:

Formulation of Nadolol multiple emulsion:^{10,11}

Method of Preparation

Multiple emulsions were created using a two-step emulsification process: a) Primary emulsification; b) Secondary emulsification.

Primary Emulsification: A total of 10 ml of distilled water, containing 25 mg of drug, was slowly added to 14 ml of an oil phase that included primary emulsifiers (Span 40, Span 60, and Span 80) and an additional 25 mg of drug. This mixture was continuously stirred at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes to produce the primary emulsion.

Secondary Emulsification: Next, 20 ml of the viscous primary emulsion was further emulsified with an external aqueous phase containing the secondary emulsifier (Tween 80) and 50 mg of drug. This step involved continuous stirring at 1000 rpm for 10 minutes. All formulations were prepared using this procedure, and the impact of different primary emulsifiers was assessed by evaluating various formulations.

Table No. 1: Formulation table for Nadalol multiple emulsion

Formulation	Drug (mg)	Span 40 (ml)	Span 60 (ml)	Span 80 (ml)	Tween 80 (ml)	Liquid paraffin (ml)	Phosphate buffer 6.8 (ml)
NME1	100	0.5	--	--	1	14	15
NME2	100	1	--	--	1	14	15
NME3	100	1.5	--	--	1	14	15
NME4	100	--	0.5	--	1	14	15

NME5	100	--	1	--	1	14	15
NME6	100	--	1.5	--	1	14	15
NME7	100	--	--	0.5	1	14	15
NME8	100	--	--	1	1	14	15
NME9	100	--	--	1.5	1	14	15

Evaluation studies of Nadalol multiple emulsion:

Organoleptic characteristics

The organoleptic properties (such as color, liquefaction, and phase separation) of both primary and multiple emulsions, stored under various conditions, were observed at several time points: 0 hours, 1 hour, 1 day, 3 days, 7 days, 14 days, 21 days, and 28 days.

Microscopic study¹³

Multiple emulsions were examined under a microscope at 100X magnification with the use of immersion oil. The study monitored the globule sizes of the prepared multiple emulsions over a period of 28 days.

Globule size

In this study, the globule sizes of the prepared multiple emulsions were measured using a light microscope equipped with a digital camera. Measurements were taken for both freshly prepared emulsions and those stored under various conditions over a period of 28 days.

Entrapment efficiency (% EE)¹²

The freshly prepared W/O/W multiple emulsions were immediately centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes. Next, 1 ml of the aqueous phase (the lower layer) was extracted using a 2 ml hypodermic syringe and diluted with phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The solution was then filtered through a Millipore filter with a 0.22 mm pore size, and the drug content was measured using a UV spectrophotometer at 267.6 nm. Encapsulation efficiency was calculated using the following equation

$$\% EE = \frac{[total\ drug\ incorporated - free\ drug]}{Total\ drug} \times 100$$

pH determination¹³

The pH values of both the freshly prepared emulsions and those stored under various conditions were measured using a digital pH meter. pH measurements were repeated for the multiple emulsions at intervals of 1, 3, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days.

Zeta Potential

The magnitude of the zeta potential indicates the potential stability of a colloidal system. Particles with a high positive or negative zeta potential will repel each other, reducing the likelihood of aggregation. Conversely, particles with low zeta potential values lack sufficient repulsive forces, leading to flocculation. Generally, a zeta potential of +30 mV or -30 mV is used as the threshold between stable and unstable suspensions. Particles with zeta potentials higher than +30 mV or lower than -30 mV are typically deemed stable. However, if the particles have a different density from the dispersant, they may eventually settle and form a dense packed bed.

In vitro drug release study

The in vitro drug release study was performed using a basic dissolution cell with a cellophane membrane (200 μm thick, breaking strength 2.7 kgf/cm). Initially, the cellophane membrane was soaked in distilled water for 6

hours, then rinsed 3 to 4 times with fresh distilled water. It was then immersed in a 5% v/v glycerol solution for at least 60 minutes and finally washed with distilled water in five separate rinses. A 15 ml portion of the freshly prepared multiple emulsion was added to the donor chamber, which was a hollow glass tube (2.5 cm in diameter and 10 cm in length) with the membrane attached to the bottom end using a nylon string. This tube was placed into a 250 ml vessel containing 100 ml of PBS at pH 6.8. The system was stirred at 100 rpm with a magnetic stirrer and kept at 37°C, acting as the receiving chamber. At set intervals, 1 ml aliquots were withdrawn from the receiving chamber, and the drug content was measured using a UV spectrophotometer at 267.6 nm after suitable dilution.

Drug release kinetics:

Data from the in vitro release study were analyzed using various kinetic models. These models included zero-order kinetics (plotting the amount of drug released versus time), first-order kinetics (plotting the logarithm of the cumulative percentage of drug remaining versus time), the Higuchi model (plotting the cumulative percentage of drug released versus the square root of time), and the Korsmeyer-Peppas model (plotting the logarithm of the cumulative percentage of drug released versus the logarithm of time). Regression analysis was used to calculate the correlation coefficients (r^2) for the linear fits of these models.

Results and discussion:

Drug and polymers compatibility studies by FTIR:

The IR spectral analysis of the drug and its physical mixtures with excipients showed that each component retained its distinct absorption characteristics, indicating no interaction between them. This suggests that no adverse chemical reactions occurred during the study, and there was no interaction between the drug and the polymer. The infrared spectra of pure drug and physical mixtures are shown in Figure no.1

Figure No. 1: FTIR spectrum of pure Nadolol

Figure No. 2: FTIR spectrum of Physical mixture

Organoleptic characteristics:**Colour**

The freshly prepared primary emulsion was creamy white in color, and there was no color change under various storage conditions, indicating stability for up to 28 days. The freshly prepared multiple emulsions were yellowish white.

Liquefaction

No liquefaction was observed in the primary emulsions under any storage conditions. For the multiple emulsions, no liquefaction occurred at 8°C (refrigerator) and 25°C (oven) over 28 days. However, slight liquefaction was noted in samples stored at 40°C in the oven on the 28th day. Liquefaction indicates instability and may result from the transfer of water from the internal to the external phase.

Phase separation

Primary emulsions did not exhibit any phase separation under any storage conditions, suggesting stability for 28 days. For the multiple emulsions, no phase separation was observed under most storage conditions, except for a slight onset of phase separation beginning on the 28th day. (Table No.2).

Table No. 2: Organoleptic properties of multiple emulsions

Time	Liquefaction			Colour			Phase separation			Centrifugation		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
0hr	-	-	-	cw	cw	cw	-	-	-	-	-	-
1hr	-	-	-	cw	cw	cw	-	-	-	-	-	-
24 Hrs	-	-	-	cw	cw	cw	-	-	-	-	-	-
72Hrs	-	-	-	cw	cw	cw	-	-	-	-	-	-
7days	-	-	-	cw	cw	cw	-	-	-	-	-	-
14days	-	-	-	cw	cw	cw	-	+	-	-	+	+
21days	-	-	-	cw	cw	cw	-	+	+	+	+	+
28days	-	+	+	cw	cw	cw	-	+	+	+	+	+

-= no change; + =slight change; cw =creamy white; ++ =no more change;
A=8°C; B=25°C; C=40°C (in oven) (n=3)

Microscopic examination

Microscopic analysis was conducted on the multiple emulsion systems, and some of the resulting images (taken at 100X magnification) are shown in Figure 3. The globule sizes of the multiple emulsions stored under various conditions were examined using a light microscope. Variations in globule sizes can indicate instability in the emulsions.

Figure No. 3: Photomicrographs of Nadolol Multiple emulsions

Globule size

Globule sizes of the multiple emulsions stored under various conditions are illustrated both graphically and in photographs. Determining globule sizes can be done using methods such as light microscopy, laser diffraction, electron microscopy, or a Coulter counter. In this study, a light microscope was utilized. Changes in globule sizes can indicate instability. Potential instability signs include the coalescence of multiple droplets with other oil drops, expulsion of individual or multiple internal aqueous droplets, merging of internal globules before expulsion leading to shrinkage, or the transfer of water from the external phase to the internal aqueous phase causing swelling and eventual rupture of the droplets.

Entrapment efficiency

The entrapment efficiency of all nine formulations was high and similar across the board.

Table No.3: % Entrapment efficiency of multiple emulsions

Formulation Code	% Entrapment efficiency
NME1	92.35
NME2	95.89
NME3	96.45
NME4	95.79
NME5	97.23
NME6	98.67
NME7	96.85
NME8	98.23
NME9	99.14

pH values

The pH was measured using a digital pH meter. The multiple emulsions had a neutral pH, which is ideal for administration, and did not cause irritation, with pH values ranging from 7.0 to 7.3 under various storage conditions.

Determination of Zeta Potential

Zeta potential was measured using a Malvern zeta-sizer instrument. This analysis helps determine the surface charge of the particles and assess their stability during storage. The magnitude of the zeta potential indicates the stability of the colloidal system. Typically, multiple emulsions with a zeta potential greater than +25 mV or less than -25 mV exhibit high stability. Particles with a high positive or negative zeta potential will repel each other, preventing the emulsion from aggregating. Conversely, if the particles have low zeta potential values, there will be insufficient repulsive force to prevent aggregation and flocculation.

Figure No. 4: Zetapotential graph of Nadolol multiple emulsion NME9

In vitro drug release

The results show that the NME9 formulation exhibits a superior release profile compared to the other formulations. Additionally, as the concentration of Span increases, the release profile of the formulation improves.

Table No. 4: In Vitro drug release studies of Nadolol multiple emulsion

Time in Hrs	NME1	NME2	NME3	NME4	NME5	NME6	NME7	NME8	NME9
	Span 40			Span 60			Span 80		
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	27	30	32	36	39	42	61	65	72
2	42	46	48	64	68	71	72	75	83
4	66	71	75	67	71	75	78	82	85
6	70	77	82	70	75	79	82	86	88
8	73	80	85	73	78	80	85	89	92
10	78	86	88	77	81	85	88	91	97

Figure No. 5: % Cumulative drug release of all formulations

In vitro drug release kinetics:

The data from the in vitro release study were applied to kinetic models to determine the mechanism of drug release from Nadolol NME9.

Table No. 5: In vitro Drug release kinetics mechanism of Nadolol multiple emulsion

Formulation code	Zero order		First order		Higuchi model		Korsmeyer-peppas		Release Mechanism transport
	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	n	R ²	
NME9	6.240	0.9944	-0.0025	0.3976	26.02	0.7439	1.0245	0.3425	Super case II Transport

The curve fitting results for the release rate profiles of the designed formulations provided insights into the drug release mechanism. Analysis of the data revealed that drug release followed a zero-order kinetics model, as it exhibited the highest linearity with an R^2 value close to one for all the prepared multiple emulsions, based on the plot of time versus percentage cumulative drug release.

Conclusion:

Multiple emulsions have been proposed for various applications, including improving bioavailability and providing extended drug delivery. Nadolol, known for its low bioavailability, has seen limited research on enhancing the bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs through multiple emulsions. This study aims to develop and evaluate a multiple emulsion formulation of Nadolol for oral drug delivery. The results indicate that Nadolol multiple emulsions were prepared using liquid paraffin and non-ionic surfactants such as Tween 80, along with different concentrations of Span 40, 60, and 80 through a two-step emulsification process. Preformulation studies, including FTIR analysis, confirmed that the functional groups of the drug were consistent with those of the standard drug and showed no interaction between the drug and the surfactants. The organoleptic properties of both primary and multiple emulsions were assessed, noting that the freshly prepared primary emulsion was creamy white. The study also investigated liquefaction and phase separation under various storage conditions. The in vitro release profiles were analyzed using different kinetic models, including zero-order and first-order equations. The results indicated that the drug release mechanism best fit the zero-order model, with the highest regression correlation coefficient. The rate constants were determined from the slopes of the respective plots, indicating the release mechanism of the multiple emulsion.

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Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest

References:

1. Joachim Allouche, Eric Tyrode, Véronique Sadtler, Lionel Choplin and Jean-Louis Salager. Single- and Two-Step Emulsification To Prepare a Persistent Multiple Emulsion with a Surfactant–Polymer Mixture. *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research*. 2003;42:3982-3988.
2. Khan AY, Talegaonkar S, Iqbal Z, Ahmed FJ and Khar RK. Multiple emulsions. *Curr Drug Deliv*. 2006;3(4):429-43.
3. Nimbekart P, Wanjarib E, Sanghid K and Gaikwad. Formulation and evaluation of sustained release multiple emulsion of hydroxyprogesterone. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2012;4:Suppl 1.
4. Gerald Muschiolik. Multiple emulsions for food use. *Current opinion in colloid and interface science*, 2007;12(4- 5):213–220.
5. Farahmand S, Tajerzadeh H and Farboud ES. Formulation and Evaluation of a Vitamin C Multiple Emulsion. 2006;11(2):255-261.

6. Hyun-Jung Kim, Julian Mc Clements D and Eric A. Decker. Preparation of Multiple Emulsions Based on Thermodynamic Incompatibility of Heat-Denatured Whey Protein and Pectin Solutions. *Food Hydrocolloids*. 2006;20(5):586-595.
7. Jim Jiao, David G Rhodes and Diane J Burgess. Rheology and stability of water-in-oil-in-water multiple emulsions containing span 83 and tween 80. *AAPS pharm sci*. 2003;5(1):62-73.
8. Dragana D Vasiljevic, Jelena V Parojcic, Marija M Primorac and Gordana M Vuleta. Rheological and droplet size analysis of W/O/W multiple emulsions containing low concentrations of polymeric emulsifiers. *J Serb Chem Soc*.2009;74(7):801–816.
9. Azevedo AF, Castro LM, Costa CI, Santos S, Matos CM and Moutinho. A multiple emulsion formulation of bacteriophage encapsulated in lipid nano vesicles. *Micro Biotec*. 2009;28-30.
10. Florence AT and Whitehill D. “The formulation and stability of multiple emulsions”, *Int J Pharm.*, 1982; 11: 277 – 308.
11. Hideaki O and Masahiro N. “Preparation and evaluation of W/O/W type emulsions containing vancomycin”, *Adv Drug Del Rev.*, 2000; 45: 5- 26.
12. Wangqi H, Kyriakos DP. *Chem. Engineer. Sci.*,1996; 51: 5043.
13. Aronson MP, Petko MF. *J. Collo. Interf. Sci.*,1993; 159: 134.